

ISic1050

I.Sicily inscription 1050

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

relief

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Quarry ('Santicelli'), near Palazzolo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140529

1. [— —] ἦ,ρ,ως ἀγαθ[ός].

2.

Edition: PHI175456

1. ἦ,ρ,ως ἀγα θ [ός].

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492678

EDCS 39102204

PHI 140529

PHI 175456

Bibliography

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